

Towards environmentally friendly Na-ion batteries: Moisture and water stability of Na₂Ti₃O₇

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Highlights

- Transformation of Na₂Ti₃O₇ into Na_{2-x}H_xTi₃O₇ ($2 < x < 0$) in contact with air or H₂O.
- First structural resolution of Na_{2-x}H_xTi₃O₇ ($x = 1.4, x = 0.7$) by neutron diffraction.
- Na_{2-x}H_xTi₃O₇ ($2 < x \leq 0$) transforms into Na₂Ti₃O₇ after the first cycle in a Na half-cell.
- CMC binder improves the electrochemical performance of Na₂Ti₃O₇.

Abstract

We report here on the moisture and water stability of the promising Na-ion anode material Na₂Ti₃O₇. Spontaneous Na⁺/H⁺ exchange is detected by PXRD after air exposure, forming solid solution compounds of the form Na_{2-x}H_xTi₃O₇ ($0 < x < 2$). By controlled ion exchange in aqueous solution two mixed compositions are prepared and their composition and structure are characterized with a panel of techniques. Both mixed compositions crystallize in *C2/m* space group like H₂Ti₃O₇, and therefore Na⁺/H⁺ exchange is found to involve a structural transition from AA stacking of [TiO₆] layers to AB stacking sequence. The electrochemical behaviour of the mixed compositions vs. Na⁺/Na is studied as well as that of an electrode of pure Na₂Ti₃O₇ prepared in water media. The water-processed electrode is shown to exhibit a superior cycling stability and therefore the results obtained highlight the potential of Na₂Ti₃O₇ as a green, low cost anode material for NIBs.

1. Introduction

Na-ion batteries (NIBs) are being investigated as a potential solution to store the excess energy produced by renewable sources because of their comparable energy density and lower cost with respect to Li-ion batteries (LIBs) [1]. Moreover, Na is one of the most abundant elements, easier to extract, and evenly distributed [2]. NIBs are thus potentially green devices with a low ecological footprint provided that environmentally friendly constituents and processing techniques are used. One of the most significant challenges in the NIBs field is to find suitable and safe anode materials able to deliver a stable capacity without the risks of operating at low voltages [3]. Indeed, graphite, which is the most common Li-ion anode material, is able to insert a very limited amount of Na⁺ hazard. Conversely, titanium-based oxides represent a promising family of negative electrode materials because of their low cost, low toxicity and easiness of preparation

44 [8]. There is a wide variety of reported titanate compounds with general formula
45 $A_xTi_nO_{2n+1}$ or $A_xTi_nO_{2n+2}$ that crystallize in layered or tunnel structures which can
46 reversibly insert Na^+ . These include $H_2Ti_3O_7$ [9], $Na_2Ti_6O_{13}$ [10], monoclinic $Na_4Ti_5O_{12}$
47 [11], $Na_2Ti_7O_{15}$ nanotubes [12], $Na_4Ti_9O_2 \cdot nH_2O$, $NaTi_3O_6(OH) \cdot 2H_2O$ [8] and $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ [13].
48 The latter is the oxide electrode with the lowest voltage ever reported (at 0.3 V vs.
49 Na^+/Na) [13]. Its structure consists of zigzag layers of edge-sharing $[TiO_6]$ octahedra (Fig.
50 S1a), stacked along the a cell axis resulting in AA $[TiO_6]$ layer stacking sequence and
51 $P2_1/m$ monoclinic space group [14]. Two types of Na^+ (Na_1 and Na_2) are located in the
52 interlayer space at 2e Wyckoff sites [14] and two additional Na^+ can be inserted at
53 additional 2e Wyckoff sites [15], leading to a specific capacity close to 178 mA h/g [13].
54

55 $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ and $H_2Ti_3O_7$ form a complete solid solution of the form $Na_{2-x}H_xTi_3O_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 2$)
56 [16-18]. The structure of $H_2Ti_3O_7$ is slightly different and is indexed with the monoclinic
57 $C2/m$ space group. In this compound the layers are displaced by $b/2$ due to the
58 formation of H bonds, which leads to a doubling of the unit cell and AB $[TiO_6]$ layer
59 stacking sequence (Fig. S1b) [17]. Two types of H^+ at 4i Wyckoff positions were reported
60 by Kataoka et al. from neutron diffraction data [19]. However, Eguía-Barrio et al. recently
61 reported an extra type of H^+ at 2a Wyckoff position for $H_2Ti_3O_7$, and therefore three
62 types of H^+ can be found in the structure which explains that the relative population of
63 the two 1H-NMR signals is 3:1 and not 1:1 [9]. Although the structure of $H_2Ti_3O_7$ is
64 similar to that of $Na_2Ti_3O_7$, it can only reversibly insert one Na^+ at 1.3 V vs. Na^+/Na and
65 H^+ are thought to be irreversibly extracted upon oxidation [9]. The structural
66 characterization of the mixed $Na_{2-x}H_xTi_3O_7$ ($0 < x < 2$) compositions is still controversial
67 because $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ and $H_2Ti_3O_7$ crystallize in a slightly different crystal structure. Izawa et
68 al. used a primitive unit cell and the same space group as $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ ($P2_1/m$) to index a
69 compound described as $Na_{1.43}H_{0.57}Ti_3O_7$ (Fig. S1a) [16]. On the other hand, Feist et al.
70 described the structure of $Na_{0.8}H_{1.2}Ti_3O_7$ with the same layer stacking as $H_2Ti_3O_7$, and
71 therefore a $C2/m$ unit cell [17]. They proposed H bond formation as the reason for this
72 (Fig. S1b). Mori et al. investigated the structure of the whole $Na_{2-x}H_xTi_3O_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 2$)
73 series by first principle calculations [18], concluding that compositions between $0 \leq x <$
74 0.75 would present an AA stacking like $Na_2Ti_3O_7$, while the phases in the range $1 \leq x \leq 2$
75 would crystallize in AB stacking sequence as $H_2Ti_3O_7$. However, the theoretical results of
76 Mori et al. have not been experimentally validated and the exact positions of Na^+ and
77 H^+ in $Na_{2-x}H_xTi_3O_7$ are not known yet.
78

79 In this work, motivated by the technological interest of $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ as anode for NIBs, we
80 revisit this system and put the focus on the moisture and water stability of this
81 compound. Both aspects are extremely relevant since they determine the storage and
82 electrode preparation conditions, which are going to have an impact in both the
83 environmental footprint and final cost of NIBs. Indeed, the use of aqueous solutions
84 instead of organic solvents to prepare slurries of electroactive materials is preferred for
85 environmental and handling reasons. Additionally, low cost environmental friendly
86 binders like carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) which is soluble in water could replace
87 polyvinylidene fluoride (PVdF), shown to form a non-stable SEI layer in $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ [20].
88

89 2. Experimental

90 2.1. Synthesis of $Na_{2-x}H_xTi_3O_7$ ($0 \leq x \leq 2$)

91 $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ (NTO7), was synthesized by mixing anatase TiO_2 (Alfa Aesar) with a 5% excess
92 of $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma Aldrich) and annealing at 800 °C for 24 h [21]. To monitor the
93 evolution of ion exchange in $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ when exposed to moisture, a powder sample of
94 NTO7 was stored in a desiccator at room temperature with a beaker full of water to
95 accelerate the process in a saturated moisture environment and PXRD patterns were
96 collected every week for a total of eight weeks. Additionally two $\text{Na}_{2-x}\text{H}_x\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ ($0 < x < 2$)
97 samples were prepared by ionic exchange. The first was prepared by soaking $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
98 in distilled water and refluxing at 60 °C for 1 day (NHTO7-H₂O), while for the second
99 $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ was soaked in a 0.1 M HCl (Panreac) solution at room temperature (RT) for 1 h
100 (NHTO7-HCl). $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ (HTO7) was also prepared by ion exchange by soaking $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ in
101 excess HCl 0.1M and refluxing at 60 °C for 3 days. After the ion exchange reaction the
102 samples were filtered and washed with distilled water and dried under vacuum
103 overnight at 60 °C.

104

105 2.2 Material characterization

106 Powder X-ray diffraction data (PXRD) were recorded on a Bruker Advance D8 instrument
107 with copper radiation ($I(\text{Cu } K\alpha_{1,2}) = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). A FEI Tecnai G2 transmission electron
108 microscopy (TEM) was used to gather electron diffraction (ED) data of the prepared
109 samples, previously dispersed in acetone and placed onto a holey-carbon film. Fourier
110 transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) data were collected in a FTIR Spectrum 400 DTGS
111 (Perkin Elmer) after diluting the sample in KBr.

112

113 Magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance (MAS-NMR) spectra were recorded
114 with a WB Bruker Advance III 500 spectrometer working at a frequency $\nu = 132.29 \text{ MHz}$
115 for ^{23}Na . The experiments were performed on powdered samples spun at the magic
116 angle with a 2.5mm standard probe. The MAS frequency was set to 20 kHz in all cases.
117 ^{23}Na spectra were referenced to a 0.1 M NaCl solution resonating at 0 ppm. The one
118 dimensional ^{23}Na -NMR spectra were recorded using a non-selective $p/2$ pulse with the
119 duration adjusted to 1.3 ms and a recycling delay of 5 s. The ^1H -NMR spectra were
120 recorded using rotor synchronized echo experiments with a $p/2$ pulse of 3 ms and the
121 recycling delay was set to 100 s. The ^{23}Na multiple quantum magic angle spectra
122 (MQMAS) were recorded using a 3 pulse basic sequence with z-filter [22]. The first two
123 hard pulses were set to 4.6 and 1.4 ms respectively, and the final soft pulse to 19 ms.

124

125 Thermogravimetric analysis (STA 449 F3 system-Netzsch) and inductively coupled plasma
126 optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES Horiba-Ultima 2 Sequential) were used to
127 quantify the amount of H^+ and Na^+ in the studied samples. Additionally, a more accurate
128 and full analysis of the composition of the samples was performed by ion beam analysis
129 (IBA) techniques at the Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (CNA) in Seville (Spain) where
130 a 3 MV Tandem accelerator is available to deliver H^+ or He^{2+} high energy beams. For this
131 analysis, two pellets of NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl were prepared. The Na, Ti and O
132 content was determined by means of Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS); a
133 beam of 1.5 MeV alpha particles was projected on the samples and the backscattered
134 particles were collected with a Si solid state detector placed at a scattering angle of 165°.
135 The intensity of backscattered particles was calibrated using a Pt standard (18×10^{15}
136 at/cm^2) so the exact concentrations could be determined. Although RBS can provide
137 very accurate concentration determination, it is not suited for the determination of H^+

138 concentration, in this case elastic recoil detection analysis (ERDA) was performed with
139 3.0 MeV He^{2+} particles at a scattering angle of 34° . With this forward scattering
140 configuration the He^{2+} incident ions drag H^+ from the sample, an Al coated Mylar filter
141 is placed between the sample and the detector in such away that the scattered He^{2+}
142 particles are stopped and only the recoil H^+ go through and are detected. Therefore a
143 signal from the H^+ concentration in the sample is obtained.

144 Powder neutron diffraction (PND) data were recorded at the D1B instrument (ILL,
145 Grenoble, France) at room temperature with a wavelength $\lambda = 1.28 \text{ \AA}$. Rietveld
146 refinements were done with the FullProf software [23]. Peak shapes were modelled with
147 a Thompson-Cox-Hastings pseudo-Voigt function. Scale factor, zero point, unit cell
148 constants, atomic positions, isotropic Debye-Waller B factors and atomic occupancies
149 were simultaneously refined. Na^+ and H^+ were located from neutron data using Fourier
150 difference maps obtained with GFourier program [23].

151

152 2.3. Electrochemical tests

153 For the electrochemical study, electrodes were prepared by mixing 80% active material
154 with 10% Carbon Super C65 (Timcal) and 10% of binder: PVdF in NMP or CMC in water.
155 The slurries were casted on battery grade aluminium foil. NTO7 laminate was dried
156 under vacuum overnight at 120°C , while NHTO7-H₂O, NHTO7-HCl and HTO7 laminates
157 were dried at 80°C . Electrodes were punched as 11 mm discs and pressed at 5 tons. All
158 electrodes were stored to an Ar-filled glove box before cell assembly. The
159 electrochemical performance was tested in Swagelok type cells vs. metallic Na disks,
160 using glass fibre (Whatman GF D 55) as separator and 1 M NaClO_4 in EC:PC (1:1,
161 ethylene carbonate: propylene carbonate) as electrolyte. Galvanostatic measurements
162 were carried out at RT in a VMP3 potentiostat (Bio-Logic) between 0.05 and 1.6 V vs.
163 Na^+/Na at a rate of 17.8 mA/g for NTO7, NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl samples, while
164 HTO7 sample was measured between 0.9 and 2.2 V vs. Na^+/Na at 20.8 mA/g [9].
165

166 3. Results and discussion

167 3.1. Moisture stability

168 The PXRD pattern of the synthesized NTO7 sample (Fig. 1) is in good agreement with the
169 already reported structure (PDF file 01e072-0148) [14] and appears free of impurities.
170 In order to verify if $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ spontaneously reacts when stored in open air, a fresh batch
171 of NTO7 has been exposed in a humid air atmosphere (to accelerate possible
172 transformations) and the evolution of the material has been followed by collecting a
173 PXRD pattern every week. These are also shown in Fig. 1, together with that of the HTO7
174 sample prepared for reference. The PXRD patterns of NTO7 and HTO7 are similar and
175 mainly differ in the position of the diffraction peaks owing to their different cell
176 parameters and the doubling along a. The evolution of the PXRD pattern of the exposed
177 NTO7 sample exhibits a progressive shift of the diffraction peaks (100) and (101) towards
178 higher 2 theta values and the appearance of new reflections which are indexed as (202),
179 (310) and (003) reflections of a $C2/m$ unit cell similar to that of $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$. This evolution
180 therefore indicates the progressive transformation into $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ by the exchange of Na^+
181 by H^+ through the formation of intermediate compositions of the $\text{Na}_{2-x}\text{H}_x\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ ($0 < x < 2$)
182 solid solution. The transformation is partial since the initial phase $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ is still found
183 in all patterns and involves a structural modification. From the intensity ratios it can be
184 estimated that after one week the amount of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ is still considerable, while almost
185 disappears in the following weeks. A widening of the diffraction peaks is also detected

186 during the transformation which can be related to the formation of smaller domains,
187 microstrains or stacking faults.

188

189 Although all patterns have been indexed using $C2/m$ space group (and therefore with a
190 doubling of the unit cell) the amount of Na^+ in the main phase can be roughly estimated
191 assuming a linear evolution of the a cell parameter following Vegard's law and using the
192 value of the subcell (Table 1). It is found that more than half of Na^+ have already been
193 exchanged in part of the sample during the first week but the transformation continues
194 to progress in the following weeks and a composition close to $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{H}_{1.5}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ is obtained
195 after the 8th week. Interestingly, $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{H}_{1.5}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ has been found to be one of the most
196 stable compositions in the work of Mori et al. [18]. Complete transformation to $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
197 has not been achieved under these conditions. The value of a parameter in the air
198 exposed samples is larger with respect to that of $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$. This can be explained by the
199 fact that these still contain Na^+ and therefore the distance between $[\text{TiO}_6]$ layers (a axis
200 corresponds to the layer stacking direction) is larger. On the other hand, it is clear that
201 neither b nor c follow Vegard's law. The b cell parameter in all cases is similar to that of
202 $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ and the value of c parameter is higher than that of $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$, most probably due
203 to the larger distortion of $[\text{TiO}_6]$ octahedra when Na^+ is present, as is discussed later.
204 Therefore, the determination of Na^+ content from the variation of the a cell parameter
205 must be taken with caution and only considered as indicative. The volume of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
206 (582.8 \AA^3) is much larger than that of $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ (542.3 \AA^3) due to the fact that in $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
207 the interlayer distance is reduced owing to the lower ionic radius of H^+ and H bonds. The
208 fact that two phases coexist and the limited amount of sample recovered did not allow
209 determining the c cell parameter with accuracy and therefore, no clear trend is observed
210 in the volume variation of $\text{Na}_{2-x}\text{H}_x\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$, although a cell parameter is found to increase
211 progressively as Na^+ amount decreases.

212

213 Fig. 1. PXRD data of pristine $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ (bottom), $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ after humid air exposure during eight weeks and
214 $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ (top).

215

216 3.2 Water stability

217 Two different samples have been exposed to aqueous solutions, one in water for 1 day
218 at 60°C (NHTO7-H₂O) and the other one in acidic solution ($\text{pH} = 1$) for 1 h at RT (NHTO7-

219 HCl). From the PXRD pattern of NHTO7-HCl sample it can be concluded that this sample
 220 is pure, while NHTO7-H₂O sample shows a small amount of Na₂Ti₆O₁₃ as impurity. This
 221 compound has been formed during the ion exchange treatment since the same Na₂Ti₃O₇
 222 batch has been used for both ionic exchange processes (Fig. S2). When Na₂Ti₃O₇ is stored
 223 8 months in the common electrolyte at 50 °C also suffers this transformation to
 224 Na₂Ti₆O₁₃ [24]. By comparing the cell parameters of these two samples with those
 225 resulting from NTO7 exposed in humid air (Table 1) it can be concluded that NHTO7-
 226 H₂O is richer in Na⁺ than NHTO7-HCl, whose composition is close to that obtained for
 227 the samples exposed to humid air between the second and third week.

228

229 Table 1. Space group, cell parameter evolution and volume per formula unit (values in brackets
 230 correspond to the equivalent volume in a supercell *2abc* to allow for comparison between Na₂Ti₃O₇ and
 231 H₂Ti₃O₇ type structures of air exposed samples compared to end-member compositions and
 232 corresponding Na⁺ amount estimated by Vegard's law using a cell parameter evolution.

Sample	Space Group	<i>a</i> (Å)	<i>b</i> (Å)	<i>c</i> (Å)	β (°)	Volume per formula unit (Å ³)	Na ⁺ amount ^a
NTO7	<i>P2₁/m</i>	8.5657(2)	3.79836(7)	9.1231(2)	101.601(2)	291.4 (582.8)	2.0
NHTO7-H ₂ O	<i>C2/m</i>	16.440(3)	3.7419(6)	9.249(2)	101.85(2)	557.3	0.80
NTO7-1st week	<i>C2/m</i>	16.419(9)	3.741(2)	9.207(4)	101.87(6)	553.4	0.70
	<i>P2₁/m^b</i>	8.550(2)	3.7744(9)	9.137(2)	101.30(2)	289.1 (578.2)	
NTO7-2nd week	<i>C2/m</i>	16.369(5)	3.733(1)	9.231(3)	102.101(3)	551.5	0.60
	<i>P2₁/m^b</i>	8.551(2)	3.7729(7)	9.132(2)	101.17(1)	298.0 (578)	
NHTO7-HCl	<i>C2/m</i>	16.369(3)	3.7498(7)	9.268(1)	103.14(1)	554.0	0.60
NTO7-3rd week	<i>C2/m</i>	16.36(1)	3.735(3)	9.243(7)	101.99(5)	552.5	0.55
	<i>P2₁/m^b</i>	8.554(3)	3.773(2)	9.139(3)	101.17(3)	289.3 (578.6)	
NTO7-7th week	<i>C2/m</i>	16.35(2)	3.736(5)	9.27(1)	102.13(1)	553.8	0.55
	<i>P2₁/m^b</i>	8.541(4)	3.785(2)	9.137(2)	101.37(4)	289.6 (579.2)	
NTO7-8th week	<i>C2/m</i>	16.33(1)	3.73(2)	9.237(8)	102.18(6)	551.0	0.50
	<i>P2₁/m^b</i>	8.533(4)	3.784(1)	9.127(4)	101.47(4)	288.8 (577.6)	
HTO7	<i>C2/m</i>	16.0243(1)	3.74973(5)	9.1888(2)	101.4384(2)	542.3	0.0

233 ^a Determined from Vegard's law. ^b Residual Na₂Ti₃O₇

234

235 The fact that no remaining Na₂Ti₃O₇ is found in any of the two samples has enabled
 236 further chemical and structural characterization. Since the space group of the two end
 237 members is different, electron diffraction (ED) data have been recorded for NHTO7-H₂O
 238 and NHTO7-HCl. Fig. 2a,b shows the pattern corresponding to [001] zone axis, which is
 239 the one most frequently found for both samples. In both cases a lattice centering is
 240 observed and therefore a centred unit cell must be used to describe the structure.
 241 According to the reconstruction of the reciprocal space (not shown) it can be concluded
 242 that both samples are isostructural to H₂Ti₃O₇ with *C2/m* space group. In the [001] zone
 243 axis, streaks along *a*^{*} are also observed which result from disorder in the stacking
 244 direction. This disorder along *a*^{*} is indicative of the existence of stacking faults that
 245 result from the gliding of the layers as the structure evolves from AA [TiO₆] layer stacking
 246 sequence (*P2₁/m* space group) into an AB stacking sequence (*C2/m* space group) and
 247 might also partially contribute to the broadening of the PXRD peaks (most probably
 248 some residual local AA motifs remain in the structure). Evidence of exfoliation along the
 249 stacking direction (Fig. S3) is observed in some particles of the NHTO7-H₂O sample as
 250 shown in Fig. 2c that are not observed in the NHTO7-HCl sample, most probably because
 251 the duration of the ion exchange treatment has been considerably longer.

252

Fig. 2. Electron diffraction patterns of [001] zone axis of a) NHTO7-H₂O and b) NHTO7-HCl samples. c) Particles image showing the exfoliation in NHTO7-H₂O sample.

To determine the exact amount of H⁺ and Na⁺ in the prepared compounds TGA and ICP-OES have been used, whose results are summarized in Table 2. From TGA analysis the amount of H⁺ can be determined from the weight loss corresponding to the release of water when the sample is heated. A weight loss of 2.39 and 4.00% is observed at 350 °C for NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl respectively. This weight loss corresponds to 0.8 and 1.4 H⁺ per formula unit. To determine the amount of Na⁺, ICP-OES analyses have been done after digestion of both samples in HCl aqueous solution, resulting in 1.3 and 0.60 Na⁺ per formula unit in NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl respectively. IBA techniques, which allow measuring Na⁺, H⁺, Ti and O amount simultaneously with high accuracy, have been also used; Na⁺, Ti and O have been determined by means of RBS whilst H⁺ concentration is obtained from ERDA measurements in the same sample (Table S1). As can be seen in Table 2, the TGA and ICP-OES results are in very good agreement with the, RBS and ERDA analysis. Therefore, we can unambiguously determine the composition of the NHTO7-H₂O sample to be Na_{1.3}H_{0.7}Ti₃O₇, while that of the NHTO7-HCl sample is Na_{0.6}H_{1.4}Ti₃O₇. As expected, the sample prepared in acidic solution contains more H⁺, even though the duration of the treatment has been shorter

Table 2. H⁺ and Na⁺ content of NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl samples obtained from TGA, ICP-OES, ERDA and RBS analysis.

	NHTO7-H ₂ O		NHTO7-HCl	
	H ⁺	Na ⁺	H ⁺	Na ⁺
TGA	0.8		1.4	
ICP-OES		1.3		0.6
ERDA/RBS	0.7(2)	1.3(2)	1.4(2)	0.6(2)

The ²³Na solid state NMR spectrum of NHTO7-H₂O is shown in Fig. 3a. The spectrum corresponds to the superposition of a number of ²³Na-NMR signals that are not resolved in a simple 1D spectrum. Due to the quadrupolar character of ²³Na (I = 3/2), second order quadrupolar broadening of the signals is normally large and precludes high resolution 1D experiments [25]. The individual components of the spectrum can be nevertheless resolved in a Multiple Quantum Magic Angle Spinning (MQMAS) experiment [26]. In this experiment, second-order quadrupolar broadening can be removed by performing a two-dimensional experiment in which multiple and single-quantum coherences are correlated in the presence of MAS. The ²³Na-MQMAS

286 spectrum of NHTO7-H₂O is shown in Fig. 3b. Using the information obtained from ²³Na-
 287 MQMAS, the spectrum of Fig. 3a can be deconvoluted and the result is shown at the top
 288 of Fig. 3b. In this spectrum, four main signals are observed, two of them with
 289 quadrupolar broadening. These two signals are characterized by values of quadrupolar
 290 coupling Cq1 = 4.1 MHz and Cq2 = 5.4 MHz and asymmetry factors h1 = 0.71 and h2 =
 291 0.54. These are similar to that observed for one type of Na (Na1) in Na₂Ti₃O₇ (Fig. S4)
 292 [21] which is a low symmetry site. Additionally, the two other main signals which show
 293 no quadrupolar broadening appear close to 0 ppm and also resemble that assigned to
 294 Na2 in Na₂Ti₃O₇ which is characterized by a negligible quadrupolar broadening, as these
 295 Na⁺ are located at a site with higher symmetry and presumably have higher mobility
 296 [21]. The accurate quantification of the distinct Na⁺ populations in the material by MAS
 297 NMR is difficult due to the different magnitudes of the quadrupolar interactions. The
 298 split of each ²³Na signal of Na₂Ti₃O₇ into two slightly different chemical shifts in NHTO7-
 299 H₂O can be attributed to the different environment generated by the partial Na⁺ and H⁺
 300 occupancies. A small additional non quadrupolar component can be related to the
 301 presence of hydrated Na⁺ at the surface of the particles. This is in agreement with the
 302 presence of ¹H NMR signal at around 4.5 ppm (Fig. 3c) indicative of the presence of a
 303 small amount of absorbed water.
 304

306 Fig. 3. a, d) ^{23}Na and b, e) ^1H solid state NMR and c, f) ^{23}Na MQMAS spectra of
307 NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl, respectively. The different components of the
308 a and d) 1D spectrum with distinct quadrupolar broadening are resolved in
309 the indirect dimension of the b and e) 2D spectrum. The resulting
310 deconvolution of the 1D spectrum considering the signals obtained in the
311 MQMAS spectrum is shown at the top of the fig. b and e for NHTO7-H₂O
312 and NHTO7-HCl, respectively.

313 The ^1H solid state NMR spectrum of NHTO7-H₂O is shown in Fig. 3c. Besides the small
314 signal arising from a minor content of water around 4.5 ppm in the sample as mentioned
315 above, one main signal is observed at around 11.5 ppm which is assigned to structural
316 hydrogen. The shift is in agreement with one of the H^+ resonances that have been
317 obtained previously in a completely protonated phase (Table S2) [9].

318
319 The ^{23}Na solid state NMR spectrum of NHTO7-HCl is shown in Fig. 3d. As for NHTO7-H₂O
320 the 1D signal can only be deconvoluted after careful inspection of the MQMAS spectrum
321 (Fig. 3e). Two quadrupolar signals are observed in this case with distinct relative
322 populations. The main ^{23}Na NMR signals obtained from the deconvolution shown in Fig.
323 3e are characterized by quadrupolar coupling constants $Cq_1 = 4.0$ MHz and $Cq_2 = 3.6$
324 MHz and asymmetry factors $h_1 = 0.66$ and $h_2 = 0.02$. Quadrupolar coupling constants
325 and asymmetry factors are in very good agreement with the values obtained for Na1 in
326 NHTO7-H₂O. This suggests that during the ion exchange process in acidic medium
327 almost all Na^+ in the Na2 position of NTO7 are replaced first, presumably due to a higher
328 mobility of Na^+ in this partially substituted site. The ^1H solid state NMR spectrum of
329 NHTO7-HCl is very similar to the one observed for the completely protonated $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
330 phase [9], with a main signal at 12.5 ppm and a minor signal at 11.5 ppm although with
331 different relative intensities (Table S2) which suggests the presence of at least two or
332 maybe three types of H^+ .

333
334 Powder neutron diffraction data of the mixed compositions were obtained at D1B
335 instrument (ILL, France) at 1.28 Å wavelength. The refinement of both neutron data has
336 been processed in several steps since the Na^+ and H^+ coordinates were unknown. From
337 the results of ED, $C2/m$ space group has been chosen to index both patterns and refine
338 the cell and profile parameters. Using the atomic structure of $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ as starting values
339 [17], the atomic coordinates of the Ti-O framework have been refined. Na^+ and H^+ are
340 then located by difference Fourier maps using GFourier program [23]. These are shown
341 in Fig. 4a,b for NHTO7-H₂O sample, where it can be seen that at $y = 0.0$ (Fig. 4a) the
342 Fourier map presents positive residual nuclear scattering density at 4i Wyckoff positions,
343 which correspond to Na^+ (Na1 and Na2) since Na^+ has a positive nuclear scattering factor
344 [27]. On the other hand, at $y = 0.5$ (Fig. 4b) negative residual nuclear scattering density
345 can be observed at 4i (H1) and 2a Wyckoff positions (H2) which would correspond to H^+
346 owing to its negative scattering factor. In the case of NHTO7-HCl sample Na^+ and H^+ are
347 found more or less at the same position as in NHTO7-H₂O sample (Fig. 4c,d,e) however,
348 one extra very intense peak appears at another 4i Wyckoff position (H3) (Fig. 4d), which
349 is indicative of three different H^+ instead of two. In this sample the negative scattering
350 intensity related to H^+ in 2a sites (H2) only becomes visible after the other two H^+ (H1
351 and H3) are included in the structural model.

352

353

354 Fig. 4. Difference Fourier maps at a) $y = 0.0$, b) $y = 0.5$, c) $y = 0.0$ and e, d) $y = 0.5$ of NHTO7-H₂O
 355 and NHTO7-HCl samples, respectively. Orange line positive and blue lines negative nuclear
 356 scattering. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader
 357 is referred to the web version of this article.)

358 The atomic positions determined from the Fourier difference maps are then introduced
 359 in the structural model to be further refined. After that, the isotropic displacement
 360 parameters (B_{iso}) and atomic occupancies are also refined by constraining the B_{iso} for the
 361 same type of atoms, with the simultaneous refinement of all parameters in the last stage
 362 of the refinement. Fig. 5 shows the Rietveld fit and the refined structures for NHTO7-
 363 H₂O (Fig. 5a,c) and NHTO7-HCl samples (Fig. 5b,d). The reliability factors obtained from
 364 PND refinement are given in Table S3, and the final atomic coordinates, isotropic
 365 displacement parameters (B_{iso}) and atomic occupancies in Table S4.
 366

367

368 Fig. 5. Rietveld refined PND pattern collected at $\lambda = 1.28 \text{ \AA}$ for a) NHTO7-H₂O (red vertical bar),
 369 Na₂Ti₆O₁₃ impurity (purple vertical bar) and b) NHTO7-HCl samples. Observed (red points),
 370 calculated (black line) and difference (blue line). Resulting structure for c) NHTO7-H₂O and
 371 d) NHTO7-HCl respectively with the corresponding Ti⁴⁺, Na⁺ and H⁺ labelled with 1, 2 and 3.
 372 The fractional occupancies of Na⁺ and H⁺ are indicating by the colour ratio. (For interpretation
 373 of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of
 374 this article.)

375 The main structural differences between both samples are therefore the negligible
 376 occupancy of Na₂ and the presence of a third type of H⁺ in NHTO7-HCl. Interestingly,
 377 also three types of H⁺ have been found in H₂Ti₃O₇ in similar positions, which is in
 378 agreement with the similar ¹H-NMR spectrum [9], the slight differences being most
 379 probably due to the fact that Na⁺ are in the interlayer spaces and its presence influences
 380 on the H⁺ environments. The fact that Na⁺ and H⁺ are located in different positions is a
 381 consequence of their different ionic radius. Indeed, Na⁺ are located in prismatic holes as
 382 in Na₂Ti₃O₇, while the smaller H⁺ are located in the same plane as oxygen (O2O), as it
 383 occurs in H₂Ti₃O₇. Only H1 is fully occupied in both compounds (note that, since it is a
 384 split position, full occupancy is 0.50 as the two neighbouring positions cannot be
 385 occupied simultaneously) and it is the first H⁺ to completely fill the position close to Na₂.
 386 Na₂ is therefore the first Na⁺ to be replaced (since Na₁ has higher occupancy in both
 387 samples) which is in agreement with the almost complete disappearance of the non-
 388 quadrupolar signal in the ²³Na solid state NMR of NHTO7-HCl sample. H₃ only appears
 389 in NHTO7-HCl and consequently this is the last H⁺ position to be occupied.

390

391 The average occupancies obtained by PND data of the rest of Na⁺ and H⁺ are given in
 392 Table S4, from which an average composition of Na_{1.3}H_{0.7}Ti₃O₇ for NHTO7-H₂O and
 393 Na_{0.6}H_{1.4}Ti₃O₇ for NHTO7-HCl has been calculated, which is in good agreement with the
 394 results of chemical analyses and solid state NMR data. Note that the amount of Na⁺

395 estimated by Vegard's law taking into account a linear evolution of the a cell parameter
396 only fits well for NHTO7-HCl sample (Table 1) which can be due to the fact that NHTO7-
397 H2O composition is close to where the symmetry change from $P2_1/m$ to $C2/m$ occurs
398 and deviates from a unique Vegard law. Compared with previously reported
399 compositions, sample NHTO7-H2O is similar to that reported by Izawa et al.
400 ($\text{Na}_{1.43}\text{H}_{0.57}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$) [16], while the composition of NHTO7-HCl is closer to that reported by
401 Feist et al. ($\text{Na}_{0.8}\text{H}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$) [17]. Despite Mori et al. predicted $P2_1/m$ for H^+ contents
402 between 0 and 0.75 by first-principle calculations [18], we have found that this is not
403 the case for $\text{Na}_{1.3}\text{H}_{0.7}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$. Whether a symmetry change occurs close to this composition
404 cannot be confirmed with our present results. In any case, for the compositions richer
405 in H^+ our indexation is in agreement with both DFT calculations and the results of Feist
406 et al.

407

408 Fig. 6 shows the different Ti environments obtained in both materials in which Ti-O
409 distances vary between 1.72(5) and 2.29(3) Å, the rest of distances are collected in Table
410 S5. Although the Ti-O bond distances are similar as in HTO7 (see Table S5) (and within
411 the same range as reported for $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ by Feist et al. (1.707(1) - 2.267(1) Å) [17] and
412 Eguía-Barrio et al., (1.72(2)- 2.25(2) Å) [9]) the octahedra are quite distorted as occurs
413 with the solid solution compositions. The bond-length distortion parameter (DI) has
414 been calculated for NHTO7-H2O and NHTO7-HCl compounds and also for the end
415 member phases (Table S6) [28,29]. The NHTO7-H2O shows more distorted octahedra
416 with respect to NHTO7-HCl and HTO7 and close to NTO7; while the DI value of NHTO7-
417 HCl is similar to that of HTO7, which indicates that the distortion is more important for
418 higher Na^+ amounts. This distortion explains the larger c cell parameter in comparison
419 with $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$. As mentioned before the a cell parameter is longer with respect to that of
420 $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ as a result of a larger interlayer space (2.78 Å and 2.62 Å for NHTO7-H2O and
421 NHTO7-HCl respectively and 2.53 Å for $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$). Interestingly, H3 (only observed in
422 NHTO7-HCl), H2 and Na1 are bonded to the same oxygen (O4). O4 is the only oxygen in
423 the structure which is bonded to one titanium atom (Ti3) and therefore has a more basic
424 character, becoming more susceptible to form H bonds which in turn are proposed to
425 be responsible of the symmetry change from $P2_1/m$ to $C2/m$. The existence of H bonds
426 is corroborated by FTIR [30], with the -OH stretching band observed in the range of 3400-
427 2900 cm^{-1} and -OH reflexions at 1630 cm^{-1} (Fig. S5).

428

430 Fig. 6. [TiO₆] octahedra of a) NHTO7-H₂O and b) NHTO7-HCl samples.

431

432 3.3. Electrochemical characterization

433 Since our results indicate that Na₂Ti₃O₇ undergoes a compositional and structural
 434 change in contact with moisture and water, the electrochemical performance of NHTO7-
 435 H₂O and NHTO7-HCl samples has been analyzed and compared to the reference NTO7
 436 and HTO7 samples. Half cells have been assembled and cycled in the voltage range of
 437 0.05-1.6 V vs. Na⁺/Na, while HTO7 is cycled between 0.9 and 2.2 V vs. Na⁺/Na, in
 438 agreement with the better results previously obtained in this voltage window [9]. In the
 439 case of NTO7, which has been carefully stored in Ar atmosphere after the synthesis to
 440 avoid the exchange of Na⁺ by H⁺, two plateaux are observed in the first cycle: one at 0.7
 441 V corresponding to the irreversible reaction with carbon Super C65 (used as conductive
 442 additive), and the other at 0.3 V, which corresponds to the reversible insertion of two
 443 Na⁺ into Na₂Ti₃O₇ [13]. As it has been previously reported, H₂Ti₃O₇ only inserts reversibly
 444 one Na⁺ at 1.3 V [9]. The electrochemical behaviour of NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl
 445 samples has similarities with both end members since three different plateaux can be
 446 observed in the first cycle at 1.25 V, 0.7 V and 0.3 V. The plateau at 0.7 V is the reaction
 447 of Na⁺ with carbon Super C65 as it occurs with NTO7, which is irreversible [13]. The other
 448 two plateaux that appear at 1.25 V and 0.3 V correspond to the Na⁺ insertion into the
 449 structure, the plateau at 1.25 V not being reversible, as shown in the derivative curve of
 450 the first two cycles (Fig. 7 a,b). The appearance of two plateaux in the first cycle is
 451 indicative of the fact that Na⁺ are inserted into different environments that are
 452 generated by the presence of both Na⁺ and H⁺ in the structure. The plateau around 1.3
 453 V was also observed when acetone is used to prepare slurries and attributed to Na⁺ by
 454 H⁺ exchange from water in the acetone [24]. In view of our results this sample contained
 455 ~0.5 of Na⁺ and therefore ion exchange possibly started before electrode preparation
 456 during air exposure to achieve this composition (Na_{0.5}H_{1.5}Ti₃O₇). In the following cycles
 457 however, the behaviour of NHTO7-H₂O and NHTO7-HCl is the same as for NTO7 (Fig.

458 7c). This suggests that in the first cycle H^+ are extracted, at least partially [9]. The mixed
 459 compositions exhibit higher capacities than NTO7 in the first discharge, although the
 460 irreversible capacity is also higher. In the following cycles their reversible capacities
 461 become close to that of NTO7, presenting a considerable capacity fading as usually
 462 found for this compound (Fig. S6) [31].
 463

464 Fig.7. dQ/dV vs. voltage for the a) first and b) second cycles. c) Voltage vs. capacity
 465 corresponding to the first and second cycle over voltage window of 0.05-1.6 V for NTO7
 466 (blue), NHTO7-H2O (red), NHTO7-HCl (green) and between 0.9 and 2.2 V vs. Na^+/Na in the case
 467 of HTO7 (black) samples. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend,
 468 the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

469 From these results it can be concluded that the spontaneous exchange of
 470 Na^+ by H^+ in $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ only affects the electrochemical behaviour of the first
 471 cycle and the material behaves as $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ from there on. In other words,
 472 the transformation into $Na_{2-x}H_xTi_3O_7$ ($0 < x < 2$) that occurs upon air or a
 473 water exposure reverts during the cycling of the battery. Therefore, it can
 474 be anticipated that water can be used as solvent in electrode preparation as
 475 well as F-free binders like CMC. This binder, already tested in hard carbons
 476 [3,32], sodium terephthalate organic electrode [33], cobalt oxide [34] and
 477 TiO_2 [35], among others, has been shown to result in better capacity retention
 478 since it covers the surface of the particles as a passivation layer [30]. In Fig. 8
 479 the galvanostatic curve of the two tested formulations (organic and aqueous
 480 medium) are compared. Contrary to the PVdF electrode, the CMC based
 481 electrode exhibits the plateau at 1.25 V in the first cycle (Fig. 8a) like NHTO7,
 482 which is indicative of a certain extent of Na^+/H^+ ionic exchange during
 483 electrode preparation (the composition is roughly estimated to be
 484 $Na_{1.6}H_{0.4}Ti_3O_7$ from the a cell parameter evolution assuming it follows
 485 Vegard's law). Although Rietveld refinement is precluded from the electrode
 486 XRD pattern, the position and intensity of the peaks can be indexed with the $P2_1/m$
 487 space group (Fig. S7), which confirms that the structural change occurs between a
 488 Na^+ content of ~ 1.3 -1.6 per formula unit. The plateau at 1.25 V disappears in
 489 subsequent cycles (as in NHTO7) and the electrode even exhibits a better
 490 performance than that prepared using organic solvent and PVdF binder. The
 491 irreversible capacity of the first cycle (which is related to the decomposition of the

492 electrolyte and in consequence with the SEI layer formation) is considerably reduced
 493 (from 56% to 37%) and the coulombic efficiency of the following cycles is largely
 494 improved (75% vs. 88% for the second cycle). Moreover, the capacity retention (Fig.
 495 8b) is drastically enhanced (63% at 20th cycle). These better capacity retention
 496 results are in agreement with recent evidence on PVdF decomposition by
 497 dehydrofluorination reaction already occurring during electrode preparation which
 498 would be a major contribution to capacity fading; as confirmed by XPS and solid state
 499 NMR [20], and demonstrates that, despite the structure and composition of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
 500 are modified when exposed to water, electrodes can be prepared in aqueous media
 501 and benefit from the positive attributes of water soluble binders like CMC.
 502

503 Fig. 8. a) Voltage vs. capacity corresponding to the first cycle and b) capacity evolution of the first
 504 20 cycle of NTO7 samples at 17.8 mA/g in the voltage window 0.05-1.6 V vs. Na⁺/Na using PVdF
 505 (blue) or CMC (black) as binder. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure
 506 legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)
 507

508

509 4. Conclusions

510 The spontaneous exchange of Na⁺ by H⁺ in $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ after air exposure leads to the
 511 formation of solid solution compounds of the form $\text{Na}_{2-x}\text{H}_x\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ ($0 < x < 2$). Two mixed
 512 compositions are prepared by ion exchange and their exact structure is solved for the
 513 first time. Both samples, for which a composition of $\text{Na}_{1.3}\text{H}_{0.7}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ and $\text{Na}_{0.6}\text{H}_{1.4}\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ was
 514 determined, crystallize in a C-centred unit cell with AB [TiO₆] layer stacking sequence
 515 ($C2/m$ space group) as $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$. Two types of Na⁺ and two types of H⁺ are found for the
 516 Na⁺-rich sample, while one extra H⁺ (H3), as in $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$, is found for the H⁺-rich sample.
 517 The electrochemical measurements show that after the first cycle the behaviour of the
 518 mixed compositions is very similar to that of their precursor $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ and therefore,
 519 although $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ is unstable when stored in air or in contact with water by exchange
 520 of Na⁺ by H⁺, this does not have a relevant impact on the electrochemical properties.
 521 This allows the use of aqueous binders such as CMC, resulting in an increase of the first
 522 cycle reversible capacity and overall better capacity retention.
 523

523

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535

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